

Effect of High-Dose Glucocorticoids on Persistent Opioid Use After Primary Total Hip or Knee Arthroplasty: Statistical Analysis Plan for a Target Trial Emulation of a Natural Experiment in Denmark

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INTRODUCTION

More and more patients are operated with total hip and knee arthroplasties (THA and TKA) due to primary osteoarthritis.²⁻⁴ The main indications are pain, reduced physical function and low quality of life.⁵

Internationally, about 10-25% of these patients continue to have moderate-severe persistent pain after surgery and approximately the same proportion remain opioid-dependent.⁶⁻⁹

Pain and inflammation in the days following surgery is associated with higher risk of persistent postsurgical pain.^{10,11} This association may be explained by upstream changes in the central nervous system (i.e. central sensitisation) caused by intense nociceptive stimuli from tissue damage.^{11,12} Glucocorticoids have marked anti-inflammatory and thereby also analgesic effects,¹³ which could impede these nociceptive stimuli and thereby reduce the risk of persistent postsurgical pain and opioid use. After two Danish trials showed short-term benefits,^{14,15} high-dose glucocorticoids were stepwise implemented as routine treatment for THA and TKA at Danish orthopaedic departments since 2012.¹⁶ However, due to concerns at single centres about adverse effects, e.g. increase risk of infection, this implementation happened gradually.¹⁶

Rationale and hypothesis

Now, administration of glucocorticoids during surgery is an established treatment following THA and TKA in Denmark. We consider it important to investigate if the routine use of high-dose glucocorticoids reduces the risk of persistent opioid use after THA and TKA. We will therefore emulate a stepped wedge cluster-randomised trial with observational data, to investigate the long-term effects of routine use of high-dose of glucocorticoids for patients undergoing primary THA or TKA (Table 1). We hypothesise that routine administration of high-dose glucocorticoids is superior to no routine glucocorticoid treatment and results in a lower risk of persistent opioid use after primary THA and TKA.

Objectives

Our primary effectiveness objective is to compare the effect of routine use of high-dose glucocorticoids (≥ 125 mg methylprednisolone or ≥ 24 mg dexamethasone) for primary THA or TKA surgery, relative to no or low dose of glucocorticoids (≤ 42.5 mg methylprednisolone or ≤ 8 mg dexamethasone), on the number of patients with persistent opioid use.

As secondary effectiveness objectives, we will assess the effect of routine use of high-dose glucocorticoids for primary THA or TKA surgery, relative to no or low dose glucocorticoids, on the number of patients with persistent use of a) prescription non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and b) prescription paracetamol use.

The safety objective is to compare the effect of routine use of high-dose glucocorticoids for primary THA or TKA surgery, relative to no or low dose glucocorticoids, on the number of days alive and out of hospital within 90 days after surgery.^{17,18}

METHODS

This is the statistical analysis plan for a natural experiment, i.e. a type of comparative cohort study. We followed the statistical analysis plan template for observational studies proposed by Watson.¹⁹ The methods sections below focus on the statistical methods and how the data will be presented in the resulting manuscript. Currently, approval for data from the national registries are pending. This statistical analysis plan was written before any data has been accessed.

Conceptually, this variation can be viewed as resembling a stepped-wedge cluster-randomized trial, in which clusters (Orthopedic departments) transition from one treatment strategy to another over time. While the timing of implementation was not randomized, treatment allocation was determined by hospital-level clinical practice rather than individual patient characteristics. This natural experiment therefore reduces most of the confounding typically encountered in conventional observational studies and provides an opportunity to estimate the causal effect of routine perioperative high-dose glucocorticoid use under real-world clinical conditions. Accordingly, the study will be analysed and reported as a target trial emulation, explicitly defining the eligibility criteria, treatment strategies, assignment procedures, follow-up period, outcomes, and causal contrasts that would have been specified had a pragmatic stepped-wedge cluster-randomized trial been conducted. The primary objective is to estimate the effect of a strategy of routine perioperative high-dose glucocorticoid administration, compared with a strategy of no routine glucocorticoid treatment, on the risk of persistent opioid use following primary THA or TKA.

Study population: All residents in Denmark have equal access to free-of-charge healthcare financed by general taxes. Each year, around 10,000 and 7,000 Danish patients undergo primary THA or primary TKA, respectively, due to primary osteoarthritis.^{2,3} Enhanced Recovery After Surgery (ERAS) guidelines are widely implemented in Denmark and half of the patients are discharged home the day after surgery.^{2,3,20}

Eligibility criteria: All eligibility criteria will be assessed at time of surgery. All adults (≥ 18 years old) who underwent elective, unilateral THA or TKA due to primary osteoarthritis between 1 January 2010 and 30 June 2024 are eligible. A patient can only enter the study once, meaning that patients undergoing more than one THA or TKA procedure, will only be analysed for the first entry. Patients with insulin dependent diabetes mellitus and patients receiving systemic glucocorticoids treatment will be excluded, as the intervention is sometimes precluded for these patients.¹³ Patients who underwent one-stage bilateral surgery are also excluded, as these procedures are rare.

Intervention: The intervention is routine use of a single high dose of glucocorticoids given after induction of anaesthesia. For each hospital, patients who underwent surgery before implementation of glucocorticoids serve as controls, while patients operated after implementation constitute the treatment arm, regardless if they received the treatment or not.^{21,22} The intervention was given along with other analgesic interventions that were routinely given to THA and TKA patients in Denmark during the study period. These include paracetamol, NSAIDs, opioids, and, for TKA patients, local infiltration analgesia.

Comparator: The comparator is no administration of glucocorticoids during anaesthesia. Patients in the control arm may have received a lower dose of glucocorticoids for postsurgical nausea and vomiting. Typical anti-emetic doses are 4-8 mg dexamethasone.²³

Study outcomes: This study has four outcomes, all assessing the real-world effect of routine use of high-dose glucocorticoids (≥ 125 mg methylprednisolone or ≥ 24 mg dexamethasone) for primary THA or TKA surgery, relative to no or low dose of glucocorticoids (≤ 42.5 mg methylprednisolone or ≤ 8 mg dexamethasone):

- a) **The number persistent opioid users (primary objective)**, defined as patients who redeemed prescriptions within at least two of the last three quarters during the first year following surgery²⁴. The first postsurgical quarter is excluded because the ICD-11 defines chronic postsurgical pain as pain “persisting beyond the healing process, i.e. at least 3 months after surgery”.²⁵ We choose to use two redeemed prescriptions in separate quarters to ensure that the patient is in fact taking the medication.²⁶
- b) **The number of persistent NSAID users (secondary objective)**, using the same ‘user’ definition as above.
- c) **The number of paracetamol users (secondary objective)**, using the same ‘user’ definition as above.
- d) **The number of days alive and out of hospital within 90 days after surgery (safety objective)**

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Assessment of variables: All included patients are observed from one year before surgery to one year after surgery. In the year before surgery, exclusion criteria and important presurgical risk factors for persistent postsurgical pain are assessed. These include whether patients have redeemed a prescription of antidepressants or benzodiazepines in the year before surgery.²⁷ Moreover, presurgical opioid use is assessed

from 3 to 12 months before surgery and defined as redeemed prescriptions within at least two of the first three quarters during the year before surgery.²⁸ We excluded the last quarter up to surgery from the definition of presurgical opioid use for two reasons. First, opioid prescriptions in this quarter may not reflect current use, but rather preparation for the upcoming surgery. Second, a study found that opioid use limited to this quarter was not associated with worse outcomes.²⁸

Other risk factors will be assessed at time of surgery, including age, sex and living alone or co-living. As described in the ‘outcomes’ section, all outcomes are assessed in the first year following surgery.

Data sources: Baseline data, including department, age, sex, type of anaesthesia, surgical access, use of local infiltration analgesia etc., will be obtained from the Danish Hip and Knee registries.^{29,30} The Danish Health Data Authority (www.sundhedsdatastyrelsen.dk/da/english) will supply data on dispensed prescriptions from the Danish National Prescription Registry, which contains all dispensed prescription medications in Denmark.³¹ Paracetamol and low-dose NSAIDS are available over the counter in Denmark, but since 30 September 2013, packs of more than 20 tablets have required a prescription. Opioids have only been available with a prescription throughout the study period. Patients’ education level and whether patients are living alone, or co-living will be assessed with data from Statistics Denmark (www.dst.dk/en).

Sample size and power considerations: Because of similarities in data structure, we calculated the power of the study as were it a stepped-wedge cluster-randomised trial.

From 2010 to 2020, approximately 127,000 and 99,000 Danish patients underwent THA and TKA surgery, respectively.^{2,3} We do not expect to include all patients operated during the study period, mainly due to limitations in access to health care records. Thus, the sample size calculation is based on 120,000 analysed patients distributed evenly between the two arms and with 15 clusters/steps. All clusters and steps were considered of equal size to simplify the calculation. The calculation is based on an intra cluster coefficient (ICC) of 0.05 and a cluster auto correlation (CAC) of 1.³² With estimated incidence of 10% and 11% persistent opioid users in the treatment and control group, respectively, the study has 90% power to obtain statistical significance at significance level of 0.05. We considered a 10% relative difference the minimal important difference.³³ This calculation was performed in R with the swCRTdesign package (version 3.3).³⁴

Data management: All eligible patients are identified from the Danish Hip and Knee Arthroplasty Registry and downloaded in an encrypted fashion to a drive with logged entry.^{29,30} These data are uploaded to

Statistics Denmark's secure online research platform in order to link with data from the Danish National Prescription Registry.³¹ All data handling will be performed in this remote-access environment, which can only be accessed with the corresponding author's digital ID. Within this environment, R statistical software with packages tidyverse, epitools, lme4, and marginaffects and will be used for data handling and analysis.³⁵⁻³⁹

Recruitment: Patients will be identified through the Danish Hip and Knee Arthroplasty Registries. These high-quality registries have had coverages well over 90% of THA and TKA operations through the study years and comprise data reported by the operating orthopaedic surgeons.^{29,30,40} These patients are screened for eligibility with data from the Danish National Prescription Registry on systemic glucocorticoid or insulin use.³¹ Patients' flow through the study will be presented in an attrition diagram (Figure 1).

Figure 1 legend: Attrition diagram to be presented in the paper. THA = total hip arthroplasty. TKA = total knee arthroplasty. NSAID = non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs

Statistical analysis

Baseline characteristics will be summarized separately for the treatment groups using appropriate descriptive statistics. Continuous variables will be reported as mean (standard deviation [SD]) or median (interquartile range [IQR]), as appropriate, and categorical variables as counts and percentages. Between-group differences in baseline characteristics will be quantified using standardized differences to assess potential imbalance and confounding. No formal statistical hypothesis testing of baseline characteristics will be performed, as baseline comparisons are intended to describe the study population rather than support statistical inference. Imbalances in patient characteristics and co-interventions are both expected, since different clusters will contribute different number of patients to the two groups. For example, a hospital that implemented high-dose glucocorticoids for patients undergoing TKA in 2011 will contribute 14 years of surgeries to the intervention group, but only patients operated from 2010 to 2011 (1 year) to the control groups. This imbalance is largely unproblematic for the causal inference in the main (adjusted) analyses.

The baseline characteristics will be presented in a Table 1.

Table 1: MockUp	Intervention group	Control group	Standardised difference
Age (years)	mean (SD)	mean (SD)	
Female sex	n (%)	n (%)	
Body mass index (kg/m2)	mean (SD)	mean (SD)	
Living alone	n (%)	n (%)	
Education attained			
Primary school	n (%)	n (%)	
Upper secondary school	n (%)	n (%)	
Vocational	n (%)	n (%)	
Academy Profession Programme	n (%)	n (%)	
University college	n (%)	n (%)	
Higher education	n (%)	n (%)	
Antidepressant use	n (%)	n (%)	
Opioid use	n (%)	n (%)	
benzodiazepine use	n (%)	n (%)	
Surgery			
THA	n (%)	n (%)	
TKA	n (%)	n (%)	
Time of surgery (years since study start)	mean (SD)	mean (SD)	
Place of surgery			
Public high-volume centre*	n (%)	n (%)	
Public low-volume centre*	n (%)	n (%)	
Private hospital	n (%)	n (%)	
Anesthesia			
General	n (%)	n (%)	
Spinal	n (%)	n (%)	
Epidural	n (%)	n (%)	
Combined	n (%)	n (%)	
Surgery duration (minutes)	mean (SD)	mean (SD)	
Local infiltration analgesia	n (%)	n (%)	

Table 1 legend: Participants' characteristics. THA = total hip arthroplasty. TKA = total knee arthroplasty. *each public department is categorised relative to the median number of annual surgeries.

Missing data:

For the main analyses, missing outcome data will not be imputed, and analyses will be conducted using the available observed data only. This approach is considered valid under the assumption that data are Missing Completely at Random (MCAR), meaning that the probability of missingness is unrelated to either observed or unobserved outcome values.⁴¹ We anticipate only limited missing data because the follow-up period is relatively short, and we expect loss to follow-up, and deaths to be infrequent and balanced between the groups. The extent of missing data will be reported transparently, including the number of participants contributing data to each analysis.

Recognizing that the MCAR assumption cannot be verified empirically and may not hold in practice, we will evaluate the robustness of the primary findings through prespecified sensitivity analyses. Specifically, worst-best and best-worst case scenario analyses will be performed by assigning the most favourable outcome value to all participants with missing data in the intervention group and the least favourable value to those with missing data in the control group, and vice versa. These analyses provide conservative bounds for the potential impact of missing data on the study conclusions.

Modelling

Crude: Unadjusted associations between implementation of routine high-dose glucocorticoids and each outcome will be estimated using generalized linear models. Binary outcomes, i.e. persistent use of opioids, NSAIDs and paracetamol, will be analysed using logistic regression models to estimate odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). Continuous outcomes, i.e. days alive and out of hospital, will be analysed using a linear regression model to estimate mean differences with corresponding 95% CIs. In these models, exposure status will be defined according to whether routine high-dose glucocorticoids had been implemented at the hospital where the patient underwent surgery. These crude analyses are intended to describe unadjusted associations and do not account for potential confounding arising from differences in patient characteristics between hospitals and temporal changes in clinical practice, such as implementation of co-interventions, decreasing length hospital length of stay, and analgesic prescribing patterns.⁴² Consequently, the primary causal analyses will rely on adjusted models designed to account for measured confounding and the stepped implementation of high-dose glucocorticoids as routine treatment.

Adjusted: The primary analyses will estimate the effect of routine perioperative high-dose glucocorticoid administration using mixed-effects regression models that account for the stepped implementation of the intervention across hospitals. All models will include a fixed effect for treatment strategy (routine high-dose glucocorticoids vs no routine glucocorticoid treatment), a categorical time-period variable to account for secular trends, and a random intercept for hospital to account for clustering of patients within hospitals.

Binary outcomes, i.e. persistent use of opioids, NSAIDs and paracetamol, will be analyzed using mixed-effects logistic regression models. Continuous outcomes, i.e. days alive and out of hospital, will be analyzed using linear mixed-effects models. Treatment effects for binary outcomes will be summarized as adjusted risk ratios (RRs) and risk differences (RDs) with corresponding 95% CIs, obtained from marginal standardization of the fitted models using the *marginaleffects* package.³⁹ Treatment effects for continuous outcomes will be summarized as adjusted mean differences with 95% CIs.

Treatment strategy will be defined according to whether routine high-dose glucocorticoids had been implemented at the hospital where the patient underwent surgery. Time period will be represented by a categorical variable corresponding to the intervals defined by the timing of glucocorticoid implementation across hospitals.²² The hospital-specific random intercept allows for correlation among patients treated within the same hospital and accounts for between-hospital heterogeneity in baseline outcome risk. This modelling approach is analogous to that used for stepped-wedge cluster-randomized trials and is intended to estimate the average treatment effect while accounting for clustering and secular changes in clinical practice over time.²²

All estimates corresponding to the contrast between groups are presented as average treatment effect with 95% confidence intervals (Table 2). Both relative differences, expressed as relative risks for binary outcomes and ratio of means for continuous outcomes, and absolute differences will be reported.⁴³ We will not adjust for multiple testing.

	Intervention group	Control group	Estimated difference		
			Crude analysis	Main adjusted analysis*	P-value
Persistent use of opioids	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)	RR (95% CI)	P=
Days alive and out of hospitals at 90 days	mean (SE)	mean (SE)	MD (95% CI)	MD (95% CI)	P=
Persistent use of NSAIDs	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)	RR (95% CI)	P=
Persistent use of paracetamol	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)	RR (95% CI)	P=

Table 2 legend: RR = risk ratio. SE = standard error. MD = mean difference. RoM = ratio of means. NSAIDs = non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs. *Adjusted for time and department.

Sensitivity and subgroup analyses:

‘Fully adjusted’: In an attempt to adjust for potential unforeseen confounders, we will conduct a sensitivity analysis, including the following patient-level covariates, including as fixed effects: Age (continuous variable), Sex (binary variable), Education level (categorical variable), Living alone or co-living (binary variable), Type of surgery (binary variable: THA/TKA), Presurgical use of antidepressants (binary variable: yes/no), Presurgical use of benzodiazepines (binary variable: yes/no) and Presurgical use of opioids (binary variable: yes/no)

‘Best-worst case and worst-best case’: To assess the impact of missing outcome data, we will conduct sensitivity analyses assigning patients lost to follow-up beneficial outcome values in the intervention group and detrimental values in the control group (best-worst case) and vice versa (worst-best case).

Subgroup analyses: In addition to the main analysis, we have planned to conduct subgroup analysis based on surgery (THA vs. TKA) and presurgical use of opioids (yes vs. no) (Table 3).

	Intervention group	Control group	Estimated difference	Contrast	P-value
Type of surgery					
Persistent use of opioids					
THA	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)	hip-knee (95% CI)	P=
TKA	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)		
Days alive and out of hospitals at 90 days					
THA	mean (SE)	mean (SE)	MD (95% CI)	hip-knee (95% CI)	P=
TKA	mean (SE)	mean (SE)	MD (95% CI)		
Persistent use of NSAIDs					
THA	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)	hip-knee (95% CI)	P=
TKA	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)		
Persistent use of paracetamol					
THA	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)	hip-knee (95% CI)	P=
TKA	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)		
Presurgical opioid use					
Persistent use of opioids					
Preoperative opioid user	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)	user-naive (95% CI)	P=
Preoperatively opioid-naïve	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)		
Days alive and out of hospitals at 90 days					
Preoperative opioid user	mean (SE)	mean (SE)	MD (95% CI)	user-naive (95% CI)	P=
Preoperatively opioid-naïve	mean (SE)	mean (SE)	MD (95% CI)		
Persistent use of NSAIDs					

Preoperative opioid user	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)	user-naive (95% CI)	P=
Preoperatively opioid-naïve	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)		
Persistent use of paracetamol					
Preoperative opioid user	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)	user-naive (95% CI)	P=
Preoperatively opioid-naïve	n (%)	n (%)	RR (95% CI)		

Table 3 legend: Results stratified by type of surgery. THA = total hip arthroplasty. TKA = total knee arthroplasty. RR = risk ratio. SE = standard error. MD = mean difference. NSAIDs = non-steroid anti-inflammatory drugs

Graphic presentations: In addition to Figure 1, i.e. the participant flowchart, we will present the main analyses in forest plots (Figure 2).

Further, we plan to present the number of persistent opioid users per calendar year in the two groups (Figure 3).

Figure 3 legend: Incidence of persistent opioid use after THA and TKA stratified by intervention group.

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